

OPENING OF ZANGAZUR CORRIDOR: A NEW STRENGTH OF THE AZERBAIJAN ECONOMY**Mammadova M.***Nakhchivan State University, Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, Azerbaijan
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ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0002-3235-2986>***ABSTRACT**

The favorable geostrategic position of Azerbaijan has historically made it possible to use its territory as an important transport hub on the routes connecting Europe and Asia. It is for this reason that the government, which has chosen this direction as one of the main areas of the non-oil sector in our country in recent years, has done a lot of work for the rapid development of transport infrastructure during the years of independence, which has led to the expansion of the geography of goods transported through the territory of Azerbaijan. However, in the future, it is necessary to implement larger regional and international projects to expand this geography and increase the country's economic power due to the transport sector.

Azerbaijan's victory in the Second Karabakh War, the liberation of the lands occupied by the enemy, and the tripartite declaration, which provides for the removal of the blockade of transport communications in the region, have opened completely new large-scale opportunities for the development of transit routes passing through our country. This, in turn, means a completely new economic power for the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, which is at the center of those routes passing through the Zangezur Corridor.

At the end of the research work, the authors concluded that with the opening of the Zangezur corridor, the prospects of strengthening the economic power of Nakhchivan are very high, which is an important factor that will lead to the growth and strengthening of the economy of Azerbaijan in general.

Keywords: West Azerbaijan, Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, trade relations, Zangezur corridor, economic power.

Introduction and Purpose.

After gaining independence, our country has had the opportunity to create an objective picture of its history and the past of its people. Truths that were kept hidden and prohibited for various reasons for many years have been revealed, and distorted events have received their true historical, cultural, and political valuation.

In the Patriotic War that began on September 27, 2020, Azerbaijan emerged victorious in 44 days and liberated its historical lands from occupation. However, a special agreement was needed to fully resolve the unstable situation in the South Caucasus. For this purpose, on November 10, 2020, a ceasefire agreement was signed in Moscow between the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan and the Prime Minister of the Republic of Armenia with the peace initiative of the President of the Russian Federation. According to the agreement signed by the region's leaders, Armenia would return the Kalbajar district to the Republic of Azerbaijan by November 15, 2020, the Agdam district by November 20, 2020, and the Lachin district by December 1, 2020. Additionally, the agreement included plans to construct a new transportation route within the next three years along the Lachin corridor (5 km wide) connecting Nagorno-Karabakh with Armenia. The agreement also contained a provision ensuring the safe movement of citizens, vehicles, and goods between the two countries in the region. The last clause of the agreement mentioned the establishment of a new transportation link between the western regions of Azerbaijan and the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic.

The purpose of this scientific article is to investigate the significance of the opening of the Zangezur

Corridor for the countries in the region and its future prospects for Nakhchivan, Azerbaijan, and the Turkish World in general. With the establishment of the Soviet government in 1920, Turkey's land connections with Azerbaijan and Nakhchivan were severed. After the Karabakh war in the early 1990s, direct transportation routes created during the Soviet era between Azerbaijan and the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic have not been utilized for nearly 30 years. The Zangezur Corridor, a transportation and railway link between Azerbaijan and Nakhchivan, opens the way for security and cooperation in the region and revitalizes the infrastructure in the region. Although the Zangezur Corridor passes through Armenian territory, the Azerbaijani administration is determined to restore transportation and railway connections with Nakhchivan based on the agreement. When this corridor is opened, Anatolia and Nakhchivan will be connected through Azerbaijan and the Caspian Sea to Central Asia. Today, there are only road and air transport links from Azerbaijan to Nakhchivan via Iran. The opening of the corridor will shorten the distance and create favorable conditions for customs clearance. The corridor will positively impact communication between the countries in the region and reduce the travel distance between Turkey and Azerbaijan by up to 400 kilometers. Once again, the aforementioned points confirm the relevance and importance of the topic.

Material and Methodology.

It should be noted that the projects for the opening and use of the Zangezur Corridor are still in the preparation stage. There are insufficient materials, textbooks, books, and scientific studies on the subject. Moreover, the lack of direct connection between Azerbaijan and

Nakhchivan for 30 years has further complicated research efforts. The collected data includes materials published in various media outlets, scientific studies after 2020, and the authors' personal research.

Economic Significance of the Zangezur Corridor.

The reconstruction of the Zangezur Corridor is planned to be carried out through the Kars-Gyumri railway line. According to this project, the total cost of constructing the Kars-Gyumri-Nakhchivan-Meghri-Baku railway line is 434 million USD. According to the forecasts of the Center for Analysis of Economic Reforms and Communication, if this project is implemented, the freight capacity on this route could reach 10 million tons after 13 years. If relations between the countries in the region improve, Armenia's trade volume with Turkey could increase from 3% to 13% of total trade. At the same time, Azerbaijan's exports could reach 1.2 billion manats (705 million USD). Among the leading sectors, the manufacturing industry is expected to see a growth equal to 3% of GDP, followed by the mining industry with 2.7%, and the raw materials sector with 2%. Overall, the independence of the Karabakh region has the potential to provide a new impetus for the development of Azerbaijan's economy in the medium term, with the agricultural sector potentially growing by 10.4%, the tourism sector by 5.5%, the mining industry by 5.3%, transportation services by 4.9%, the manufacturing industry by 4.3%, and other services by up to 1.4%. Therefore, the income obtained from the non-oil sector could potentially create 5.1% of GDP.

According to another analysis by the Center, the volume of exports is expected to rise to 710 million USD with the revitalization of transportation. The opening of the corridor will also allow the government to save 10 million USD annually, which it currently spends subsidizing Baku-Nakhchivan flights. The Zangezur Corridor will gradually eliminate the costs of transit fees, currently paid as 15% for gas transit from Azerbaijan to Nakhchivan through Iran. New opportunities for a railway line between Russia and Iran will be opened, and in the future, Armenia will also benefit from the opportunities provided by this corridor.

The Communicative Significance of the Zangezur Corridor.

It is known that the Zangezur Corridor includes not only railway but also road communications. The railway consists of the Horadiz-Aghband road, the 44 km long Zangezur section, the Armenia-Ordubad and Ordubad-Nakhchivan-Yerevan, Yerevan-Gyumri-Kars borders. It should be noted that the construction of the Kars-Iğdir railway, planned to be connected to Nakhchivan, began in 2020. In addition to this direction, the railways of the South Caucasus and Iran intersect at the Julfa crossing. As for the road transport passing through Zangezur, before the start of the Armenia-Azerbaijan conflict in the early 1990s, there was a route from Nakhchivan passing through Armenian territory to Karabakh and beyond. Naturally, this route now needs to be practically rebuilt, but it was a quite cost-effective transport communication in terms of both freight and passenger flow.

It is particularly noteworthy that the more significant advantages of opening the corridor are, of course, the maximum simplification of delivering goods from Nakhchivan to the rest of the country and vice versa, as well as to the world market. As a result of all this, the economic development of the autonomous republic, after long years of difficulties related to a virtual blockade, will receive a strong impetus with the opening of the Zangezur Corridor. Additionally, Azerbaijan will have the opportunity to implement new infrastructure projects in this region and significantly reduce its dependence on Iran in solving the energy and gas supply problems of Nakhchivan.

The International Importance of the Zangezur Corridor.

The Zangezur Corridor is characterized as an important project from social, economic, geopolitical, and geostrategic perspectives that can more easily connect Azerbaijan, China, Central Asia, and even Armenia and Europe. The reduction of military and political conflicts in the region is seen as a reason for increased trade between countries. Moreover, it will accelerate the expansion of the railway line between Russia, Azerbaijan, Turkey, Armenia, and Iran and lead to the opening of many trade routes, thereby increasing trade volume in the Caucasus region. With Azerbaijan becoming a transportation hub of Eurasia, the roads and railways in the Caucasus region will create new competition and opportunities by increasing the transit security of the region. Naturally, in this context, the construction and routes of the East-West and North-South international transportation corridors, as well as the construction of the oil and gas pipeline system extending from the Caspian Sea to Europe, will bring new developments. The importance of Azerbaijan's East-West and North-South transportation corridors will further increase.

Located on the historical Silk Road, Azerbaijan is undertaking comprehensive work as a logistics center between Europe and Asia. The East-West Corridor, Iron Silk Road, and Europe-Caucasus Transportation Corridor (TRACECA) projects are very important for the realization of projects in the region. The Zangezur Corridor will positively impact the economy of the South Caucasus and Central Asia along the China-Europe Central Corridor, creating extensive opportunities for the development of Nakhchivan. With the increased significance of South Caucasus transportation, the opportunities to connect Europe and Asia will improve. Solving potential transportation problems on the Baku-Tbilisi-Kars railway line in the future will enhance China's ability to deliver goods to Europe in the shortest way. The entry point, which includes 4256 kilometers of railway and 508 kilometers of sea route, extends from the shores of China-Kazakhstan to Azerbaijan (via the Caspian Sea) and from Georgia to Turkey. The Baku-Tbilisi-Kars (826 km) and Dirne-Kars (1388 km) railway lines have strategic significance within the Central Valley framework. It is considered easier and more economical to transport China's goods to Europe via the Central Corridor rather than the Northern channel passing through Russia. For information, goods from China reach Europe in 20 days via the Trans-Si-

berian route and in 12 days via the Central Transmission. Shipping goods from China to Europe by sea takes 36 days.

The significance of opening the Zangezur Corridor does not bypass Iran either. It provides access to the Bandar Abbas cargo port in Iran and the Istanbul-Islamabad railway line, as well as to the Gulf of Oman and the Indian Ocean in the South Caucasus.

Conclusion and Proposals.

In summary, we can say that the opening of communication corridors in the South Caucasus, particularly in Zangezur, will not only strengthen Azerbaijan's position as a transportation-logistics link at the crossroads of Europe and Asia but also allow the region to utilize its rich economic potential. This will lead to improved welfare for all countries in the region.

Discussion and Conclusion.

In conclusion, the Zangezur Corridor undoubtedly offers new opportunities for many transit transportation projects connecting Asia and Europe through Azerbaijan. This will strengthen Azerbaijan's position as a transportation and logistics hub of Eurasia in the near future. With the construction of railways and roads, the Zangezur Corridor is expected to create an investment environment in the region, especially for small and medium-sized enterprises, thereby contributing to the development of the country's economy. On the other hand, the main advantage of this project will be that this economic contribution and transportation infrastructure advantage will not be limited to Nakhchivan and Azerbaijan but will also yield significant positive results on

a regional scale. From this perspective, the Zangezur Corridor should be regarded as an invaluable project with the potential to contribute to the economic development of the countries in the region, including Armenia. Additionally, the development of infrastructure projects in the countries of the region and the creation of new investment opportunities are among the expected outcomes.

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